

VAN Katrien Weyns
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NOTA

Demonstration at DH Benelux 2025

Much to discover. KADOC's large datasets and their research potential

For nearly fifteen years, KADOC-KU Leuven has been digitizing the heritage of private individuals and organizations in order to better manage and make it available.¹ Digitization is done both systematically for specific series, on a project-by-project basis in partnership with other heritage institutions, and at the request of readers. This led to a collection of more than 3.5 million identified digital objects available to researchers. This set contains very rich but virtually unexplored series that we are bringing to attention during an interactive demonstration.

The ways religion has manifested itself in Belgian society since 1750 is the focus of documentary heritage collection building at KADOC. Not only documents of religious communities are present in the KADOC collection, but also religiously inspired initiatives such as educational projects, charitable organizations, professional associations, international umbrella associations and cultural organizations. The archives and publications are therefore very diverse in nature and content. To facilitate their management, series were created. In this way, several large series of content-mixed, but materially uniform, documentary heritage were created that have been systematically described and are now accessible digitally.

During a demonstration we will dive into these series of several thousand objects. The historical sources will be “on display” and we will reflect together with attendees on their research potential, new projects and possibilities. For example, the collection of postcards identifying and locating historic interiors and buildings in Belgium is a valuable resource for art historical research, but are there other possible tracks.² The collection of photo albums are also highlighted. They were brought together from various archives and contain images of buildings, public events, youth camps,

¹ <https://kadoc.kuleuven.be/english/index>.

² KADOC-KU Leuven, Collection postcards, 1903-2000. <https://abs.lias.be/Query/detail.aspx?id=1512337>

meetings of associations, trips, family snapshots, and so on.³ The photo albums of missionaries stand out with sometimes images from around 1900 from countries such as Congo, Rwanda, Burundi, China, Canada, ... Historical research into representation within delineated parts of this collection could be a track to follow. The poster collection is very large and contains images and drawings relevant for stylistic or promotional research, for example.⁴ The more than 50 000 film files of Filmmagie, the Catholic Film League, includes the former collection of Docip with press clippings, film reviews, notes and promotional material of films from the 1930s to 2000s.⁵ This corpus is therefore relevant for image analysis as well as text analysis. In addition, KADOC manages particularly large collections of moving image and audio clips (about 29 000 digitized items) of major and minor events in Catholic circles in the second half of the twentieth century. The large subcollections of “third-party broadcasts”, airtime that religious communities among others received, is a nice subset to start from for discourse analysis, sentiment analysis, and so on. In the demonstration, we focus on the television broadcasts about agriculture produced by Boerenbond, a catholic farmers union.⁶ Finally, the periodicals are considered, with some newspapers and specialized magazines. First, an almost full collection of Flemish parish journals dating from the beginning of the twentieth century to today is available for research.⁷ This newspaper was popular in catholic circles and contains details about parish communities and the local events within that parish. Second, some long running mission journals are presented containing pictures and representations of cultures and nature in the mission.⁸ These journals are unlocked with OCR recognition and thus full text searchable.

These collections are obviously closely related to each other and to paper archives that are kept at KADOC, many of which have not been digitized but which allows for deeper analysis. In addition,

³ KADOC-KU Leuven, Collection photo albums, [1800]-1970. <https://abs.lias.be/Query/detail.aspx?id=1636220>

⁴ KADOC-KU Leuven, Collection posters, 1699-2020. <https://abs.lias.be/query/detail.aspx?id=1493526>; Keith Johnston directed methodological update for promotional research in 2019: Johnston, Keith M. “Researching Historical Promotional Materials: Towards a New Methodology.” *Historical Journal of Film Radio and Television/Historical Journal of Film, Radio and Television* 39, no. 4 (2019): 643–62. doi:10.1080/01439685.2019.1615293.

⁵ KADOC-KU Leuven, Collection film files Filmmagie/Catholic Film League, 1930-2000. <https://abs.lias.be/Query/detail.aspx?ID=886364>

⁶ KADOC-KU Leuven, Audiovisual archive of Belgische Boerenbond, subcollection ATRO, 1981-1997. <https://abs.lias.be/Query/detail.aspx?id=1752769>

⁷ KADOC-KU Leuven, Collection parish journals. https://kadoc.limo.libis.be/discovery/collectionDiscovery?vid=32KUL_KADOC:KADOC&collectionId=815834000001480

⁸ KADOC-KU Leuven, Collection mission journals. https://kadoc.limo.libis.be/discovery/collectionDiscovery?vid=32KUL_KADOC:KADOC&collectionId=818032625001480

these time documents have been contextualized by reference to structured authority data on related individuals and organizations, making it easier to map networks and interpret the material correctly. KADOC, meanwhile, continues to work on creating further accesses through AI techniques such as named entity recognition, speech to text, text extraction. However, this remained experimental and there is still much to learn. The possibilities AI creates are enormous, but resources are limited. Input for further development of such retrieval initiatives is therefore welcome.

We invite researchers to unleash their creativity and expertise and brainstorm new projects and directions during the demonstration.

Katrien Weyns